

1 **Active disease in the blood in humans with CD is marked by expression of CD177 and a suite of FC**
2 **receptors.**

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7 Inflammatory bowel disease includes Crohn's Disease and Ulcerative Colitis distinguished by depth of
8 penetration in the bowel wall, location of disease in the GI tract, and other features. Sedimentation rate of
9 the red blood cell (ESR) and C-reactive protein (CRP) are used as surrogates or markers of inflammation
10 in the blood to detect and measure inflammation associated with disease activity. We identified CD177 as
11 a marker of disease activity in the blood in humans with inflammatory bowel disease. Together with
12 CD177, we also identified a suite of cell surface Fc receptors that appeared to define a major
13 representative component of disease activity of in the blood in patients with CD. The genes that encoded
14 these receptors included Fc gamma receptor (FCGR1A), Fc alpha receptor (FCAR), Fc epsilon receptor
15 (FCER1A), FC gamma receptor 2C (FCGR2C), in addition to the pseudogene transcripts *FCGR1CP* and
16 *FCGR1BP*. A systems level approach to discovery of FC receptor associated mechanisms of action
17 identified a panel of immune receptors whose expression functioned in toleragenic processes or likely
18 assisted in distinguishing self versus non-self in the gastrointestinal tract including IGSF6, LILR receptors
19 LILRA5 and LILRB3, TYROBP, PILRA, PILRB, Siglec9, FPR1, MS4A7 and MS4A6A, MND A and Clec10A.
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